

Enhanced Student Enrollment and Grade Module

Ma. Louise Pace P. Jusay; Michael M. Orozco, DIT

Author:

Ma. Louise Pace P. Jusay

Graduate Student, Master of Science in Information Technology

University of Perpetual Help System Laguna, Philippines

Email: [c22-2612-714](tel:22-2612-714) @uphsl.edu.ph, mlpjusay@gmail.com

Co-author:

Michael M. Orozco, DIT

Adviser, University of Perpetual Help System Laguna, Philippines

Email: orozco.michael@uphsl.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

The educational system is an area in which the influence of technology has been most profound. The study focused on the enhanced student enrolment and grade module. The study sought answers to the following: 1. What is the level of performance of the enrolment system before and after as to: number of forms to be filled up; waiting time; and payment method? 2. What is the level of acceptability of the system as to the following: functionality; reliability; usability; efficiency; maintainability; and portability? 3. What is the level of effectiveness of the system in relation to the abovementioned characteristics? And 4. Is there a significant difference before and after the utilization of the enhanced enrolment system and grade module as assessed by the respondents? The study utilized both descriptive and developmental methods in the context of system design and evaluation, with emphasis on how these techniques were used in software development and system enhancement initiatives. The respondents of the study were administrators, faculty and students. With the enhanced enrolment system, it is paperless enrolment from the initial stage up to the viewing of grades of the students. The respondents found the present system as acceptable and effective using the ISO/IEC 25010 software quality metrics.

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INTRODUCTION

Technology has turned into an inseparable piece of the existence of the individual. A day without technology is like an isolated chamber in which no one is connected to the outer world. The omnipresence of technology may be apparent in the smartphones in our pockets, but even more so in the complex algorithms that influence the online experience. While it offers overwhelming opportunities for progress and connection, it also presents a complex web of challenges that demand careful consideration.

The educational system is an area in which the influence of technology has been most profound. At present, technology is widespread in educational milieu. The people need interconnection where it transformed business, education, and social interactions, enabling collaboration and knowledge sharing. Moreover, technology has expanded access to information, Search engines and online databases allow rapid knowledge retrieval, facilitating learning and exploring new concepts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ISO/IEC 25010 software quality metrics were used as guide posts in developing a system that can help institutions improved their enrolment system. The importance of regular maintenance practices in sustaining the performance of enrollment systems in higher education cannot be dispensed with.

Villaruz (2024) designed to assess and optimize the enrollment process of higher education institutions called A Rule-Based Decision Support System (DSS). It was built using a rules engine

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that simulates human decision-making logic, the system could assess student qualifications, available course slots, and scheduling conflicts in real-time. It was anchored on ISO/IEC 25010 software quality metrics, particularly under the functionality characteristic which revealed that the system was highly dependable in producing accurate and consistent decisions based on set criteria. This functionality directly contributed to minimizing human error, reducing enrollment disputes, and providing transparency in course allotments.

As a result, Grepon (2021) designed, developed and evaluated a School Management Information system (SMIS) aimed at improving the operational efficiency of a community college. The administrators assessed and highlighted its capacity to accurately perform data-driven tasks, automate repetitive workflows, and provide real-time access to student data.

Additionally, Bonalos, (2025) opined that the reliability of any system developed is the cornerstone of trust and user adoption. Institutions that aim to transition from manual to digital systems must ensure the software can handle high-demand tasks while preserving data integrity.

The idea of Bonalos (2025) was based on Baran's (2021) research which concluded that reliability is fundamental in educational systems, particularly during time-sensitive processes like enrollment. He contended that the system had built-in redundancies and automatic data backup protocols to further ensure reliability in case of unforeseen technical glitches.

Similarly, Bejar (2023) evaluated the Dess Application Program (DAP) used at Lamlifew IP Integrated School through the lens of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The authors investigated three usability components—Perceived Usefulness (PU), Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), and Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU)—among respondents comprising both students and faculty.

Institutions or schools using technology are mindful of the latest trends. Santos (2023) was not exempted. He studied how the proficiency level of users (students and staff) affects the quality of academic services, focusing specifically on enrollment and academic records systems. The study argued that high system proficiency leads to faster processing times, fewer support requests, and higher satisfaction ratings. It also found that proficient users reported a better understanding of

system updates and new features. The authors stressed the need for continuous capacity-building programs and recommended integrating in-app tutorials, user guides, and real-time support within enrollment systems to elevate user proficiency levels.

Lindbergh (2023) made a study which focused on maintenance protocols like system updates, bug fixes, and performance optimization measures, which were found to enhance long-term system reliability and prevent downtime.

Enrollment systems can remain portable without sacrificing performance. By analyzing different implementations across five universities, Alcantara (2022) identified best practices like cloud hosting, minimal use of proprietary libraries, and adherence to web standards (HTML5/CSS3) for cross-platform support. The literature noted that portable systems reduced institutional costs and improved student experience by removing device-specific limitations. It also highlighted that scalable and portable systems were better suited for disaster-prone or low-connectivity regions, allowing access regardless of time or place.

Consequently, Lopez (2024) assessed the real-world performance of enrollment systems used in 10 institutions across the Visayas Region, focusing on how well these systems performed on various devices (smartphones, tablets, laptops) and browsers (Chrome, Safari, Firefox, Edge). Results showed that only 60% of the systems were fully portable, with common issues including layout misalignment and feature inaccessibility on mobile devices. The study emphasized the importance of mobile-first design principles and suggested that universities invest in adaptive testing before system deployment. Institutions that employed responsive web design had higher student engagement rates and lower system complaint rates.

METHODOLOGY & TECHNIQUES USED

The study used a combined developmental and descriptive research design. Developmental design entails continuous evaluation and development, with each phase building on the one before it to improve the system's overall effectiveness, usability, and functionality (Clarke-Plaskie, et al

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(2022). Descriptive research design, on the other hand, provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject (Sirisilla and Sirisilla, 2023). The study focused on the enhanced student enrolment and grade module. It used a researcher made questionnaire to answer the research problem. The study sought answers to the following: 1. What is the level of performance of the enrolment system before and after as to: number of forms to be filled up; waiting time; and payment method? 2. What is the level of acceptability of the system as to the following: functionality; reliability; usability; efficiency; maintainability; and portability? 3. What is the level of effectiveness of the system in relation to the abovementioned characteristics? And 4. Is there a significant difference before and after the utilization of the enhanced enrolment system and grade module as assessed by the respondents? The respondents of the study were the administrators, faculty, IT experts and students in a state university in Metro Manila. The study was conducted from January – May, 2025.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of performance of the enrolment system before and after the enrolment system

The present enrolment system is using the advisement form which takes about 15-20 minutes to be filled up by the students while the enhanced enrolment system is a paperless system where students need not fill up any form at all but will only wait for about 3 minutes to generate the Certificate of Enrolment after encoding the needed information. The waiting period is comparatively lessen as it is an online enrolment. The payment method, on the other hand, of the tuition fee was quite a challenged to the students as it was on a CASH BASIS only. On the average, payment took about 30 minutes to an hour payment to be successful notwithstanding the number of students waiting to be served by the Cashier's Office. With the enhanced enrolment system and grade module, it takes about 3-5 minutes to click the button and pay the tuition fee.

2. Level of Acceptability of the Enhanced Enrolment System and Grade Module

Table 1

Level of Acceptance of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: System Performance

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	W	VI	WM	VI
1. The system performs reliably without crashing or freezing	3.20	A	3.20	A	3.20	A
2. The system is consistently available and has minimal downtime	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.25	A
3. The system maintains a consistent performance without lag or delays over extended usage.	3.30	SA	3.60	SA	3.45	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	SA	3.33	SA	3.30	SA

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Acceptable (SA)

1.75-2.45 Moderately Acceptable (MA)

2.50 – 3.25 Acceptable (A)

1.00-1.74 Least Acceptable

As to the level of acceptability on system performance, administrators assessed the system performance with the weighted mean of 3.26 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable and the Faculty with weighted mean of 3.33 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable. The composite mean was 3.30 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable;

The results imply that the system performance of the enhanced enrolment system and grade module is found to be accepted and therefore performs as expected by the different stakeholders.

The findings are supported by Silva, et al when they mentioned about the portability and usability of Open Educational Resources on Mobile Devices which are freely access, openly licensed hypertext, audio video, simulations, games and animations that are useful for teaching and learning purposes.

Table 2

Level of Acceptance of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: System’s Functionality

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The enrollment system allows me to easily register students for courses without errors.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA	3.20	A
2. The grading system allows me to generate comprehensive reports (e.g., individual student grades, overall class performance).	3.70	SA	3.40	SA	3.25	A
3. Enrolment system and grading sheet.	3.60	SA	3.40	SA	3.45	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	SA	3.60	SA	3.30	SA

With system’s functionality, administrators got overall weighted mean of 3.77 and the faculty got 3.60 both verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable with the overall weighted mean of 3.30 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable.

This implies that the system’s functionality of the enhanced enrollment and grade module is highly regarded by the respondents. This will help the users of the enhanced enrolment and grading sheet when they will maximize its functionality.

The findings are supported by Tamrakar and Mehta (2011) where they claimed that learning through Information Technology be empowered through Information Technology (IT) to ensure quality education.

Table 3

Level of Acceptance of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: System’s Usability

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The enrollment system is easy to use and navigate for registering students.	3.5	SA	4.00	SA	3.75	SA
2. The enrollment system provides clear and understandable instructions or feedback when errors occur	3.40	SA	3.40	SA	3.20	A
3. The grading sheet system allows me to easily find and correct errors in the student grading process.	3.60	SA	3.40	SA	3.50	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	SA	3.53	SA	3.48	SA

As to the System’s Usability, the administrator obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable while the faculty had an overall weighted mean of 3.53 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 3.48 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable.

The results imply that the enhanced enrolment system and grading sheet is favored by the respondents. It can be seen that the system will help the different stakeholders as they found the system as friendly-user to everyone who may want to use it.

The study of Andaya (2020) examines the program’s effectiveness in terms of curriculum relevance, teacher competency, resource adequacy, and student outcomes.

Table 4

Level of Acceptance of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: System’s Security

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The enrollment system is easy to use and navigate for registering students.	3.5	SA	4.00	SA	3.75	S A
2. The enrollment system provides clear and understandable instructions or feedback when errors occur	3.40	SA	3.40	SA	3.20	A
3. The grading sheet system allows me to easily find and correct errors in the student grading process.	3.60	SA	3.40	SA	3.50	S A

Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	SA	3.53	SA	3.48	S
						A

On the System’s Security, the administrators garnered an overall weighted mean of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable and the Faculty got 3.53 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 3.48 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable.

This implies that the enrolment system and grading sheet is secured and protected when it will be used by the users of the system. This follows the data privacy act where it protects the personal information of the users of the system. Moreover, the users will feel complacent and confident that the data will not be hacked by anyone.

The findings are in consonance with Gordon (2020) who said that there is a wide range of approaches in policy evaluation processes, reflecting different contexts ad priorities. Further, robust policy evaluations are supported by strong institutional frameworks, including clear mandates, adequate resources, and stakeholder engagement.

Table 5

Level of Acceptance of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: System’s Compatibility

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The grading sheet system is compatible with other tools or software I use	3.40	SA	4.00	SA	3.75	SA
2. The grading system correctly handles different grading formats	3.40	SA	3.20	A	3.30	SA

(e.g., letter grades, numerical scores, pass/fail) without errors.

3. The grading sheet system is compatible with other tools or software I use	3.33	SA	3.60	SA	3.50	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	SA	3.53	SA	3.50	SA

The administrators rated the indicators with an overall weighted mean of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable and the Faculty with 3.53 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable. The overall weighted mean was 3.50 verbally interpreted as Strongly Acceptable.

This confers that the respondents saw the enrolment system and grading sheet as compatible to the other systems that they already knew and therefore, they will not encounter difficulty at all in the use of the enhanced enrolment system.

The findings are supported by the study conducted by Sales (2022) where he said that both students and teacher expressed general satisfaction with the SHS curriculum, acknowledging that it addressed the need for a more holistic and skill-based education.

3. Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrolment System and Grade Module

Table 6

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: Functionality Suitability

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI

1. The set of functions covers all the specified tasks and intended users' objectives.	3.30	HE	3.40	HE	3.35	HE
2. The system provides accurate results when used by intended users.	3.70	HE	3.40	HE	3.55	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	HE	3.40	HE	3.45	HE

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00 Highly Effective (HE)
(ME)

1.75-2.45 Moderately Effective

2.50 – 3.25 Effective (E)

1.00-1.74 Least Effective (LE)

The administrators obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective and the Faculty got an overall weighted mean of 3.40 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.45 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

This implies that the enrolment system and grade module is ideal and practical for the utilization for the enrolment period. It does not task the users with its complexities, hence, friendly users to everyone although it is highly technology inclined.

This is supported by Nevo (2022) relative to the practice of self-evaluation has been institutionalized through tools which guides schools in analyzing their performance systematically.

Table 7

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: Performance Efficiency

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI

1. The response time and throughput rates of a product or system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.	3.40	HE	3.40	HE	3.40	HE
2. The amounts and types of resources used by a product or system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.	3.40	HE	3.40	HE	3.40	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.40	HE	3.40	H E	3.40	HE

As shown in the table, the administrators and Faculty assessed the different indicators for this aspect with an overall weighted mean of 3.40 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.40 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

This implies that the system is found to be efficient when it will be used by the different stakeholders as shown with the level of acceptability of the respondents. This means that they will not encounter difficulty whenever they will engage the system as they intend to use it.

The results are supported by Brown, (2021), despite policy endorsements, actual engagement of students and parents in school evaluations is often limited and mainly tokenistic, with little evidence of significant impact on school practices.

Table 8

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: Interaction Capability

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Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The functions of a product or system can be learnt to be used by specified users within a specified amount of time.	3.40	HE	3.80	HE	3.60	HE
2. System has attributes that make it easy to operate and control.	3.00	E	3.60	HE	3.30	HE
3. User interface presents functions and information in an inviting and motivating manner encouraging continued interaction.	3.40	HE	3.80	HE	3.60	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	HE	3.40	HE	3.50	HE

As displayed in the table, the administrators assessed the indicators with an overall weighted mean of 3.26 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective which was lower than the overall weighted mean of the Faculty with 3.40 overall weighted mean verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.50 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

This implies that with the interaction capability, the system is capable to send messages to the users, thereby, it is interactive with the users when asked of something about the system. There is a ready answer or response made when the needs arise.

The findings are supported by Campos, (2023), the educational system has been significantly shaped by various colonial periods, each contributing to the structure and content of education in the Philippines.

Table 9

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by Administrators and Faculty: Flexibility

Indicators	Administrators		Faculty		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. A product or system can effectively and efficiently be adapted for or transferred to different hardware, software or other operational or usage environments.	3.40	HE	3.80	HE	3.60	HE
2. The product can handle growing or shrinking workloads or to adapt its capacity to handle variability.	3.30	HE	3.40	HE	3.35	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.35	HE	3.60	HE	3.50	HE

As alluded in the table, the administrators rated the indicators lower than the Faculty respondents with the overall weighted mean of 3.35 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective while the latter assessed the indicators with an overall weighted mean of 3.60 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.50 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

Table 10

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by School Administrators and IT Experts: Reliability

Indicators	Administrators	IT Experts	Composite
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	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The system, product or component performs specified functions without fault under normal operation.	3.60	HE	3.40	HE	3.50	HE
2. The system, product or component is operational and accessible when required for use.	3.60	HE	3.20	E	3.40	HE
3. The system, product or component operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.	3.80	HE	3.60	HE	3.70	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.35	HE	3.60	HE	3.50	HE

As suggested in the table, the Administrators rated the different indicators with an overall weighted mean of 3.35 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective while the IT experts rated them with an overall weighted mean of 3.60 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.50 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

The results imply that the enhanced enrolment is found to be favorable by the respondents. Although there is a slight difference in the assessment of the respondents, they concurred that the enrolment system and grading sheet is flexible to be used in the school system.

The findings are supported by David (2022) when he suggested that addressing these issues on education is essential for enhancing the quality of education and improving the country's performance in both local and international assessments.

Table 11

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by School Administrators and IT Experts: Security

Indicators	Administrators		IT Experts		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product or system ensures that data are accessible only to those authorized to have access.	3.80	HE	4.00	HE	3.90	HE
2. The system, product or component ensures that the state of its system and data are protected from unauthorized modification or deletion either by malicious action or computer error.	3.60	HE	3.40	HE	3.50	HE
3. The identity of a subject or resource can be proved to be the one claimed.	3.40	HE	4.00	HE	3.70	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.57	HE	3.80	HE	3.70	HE

As delivered in the table, the administrators and IT experts assessed the indicators, more or less, similarly with the overall weighted means of 3.57 and 3.80 respectively both verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean was 3.70 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

The results imply that the enhanced enrolment and grading sheet is reliable. The respondents can be used with consistency since the reliability has been established by the system. The same data will be released as when the users will ask for the information with the use of the new system.

The findings are supported by Baran (2021) when he assessed the system under ISO 25010 software quality characteristics where users experienced minimal disruptions, delays or crashes even during peak enrollment periods.

Table 12

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by School Administrators and IT Experts: Maintainability

Indicators	Administrators		IT Experts		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can be used as an asset in more than one system, or in building other assets.	3.60	HE	4.00	HE	3.80	HE
2. The product or system can be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading existing product quality.	3.40	HE	3.60	HE	3.50	HE
3. Effectiveness and efficiency with which test criteria can be established for a system, product or component and tests can be	3.80	HE	3.20	E	3.50	HE

performed to determine whether those criteria have been met.

Overall Weighted Mean 3.60 HE 3.60 HE 3.60 HE

As presented in the table, both the administrators and IT experts agreed on the maintainability of the system as they have the same weighted means of 3.60 in all indicators with verbal interpretation of Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean for maintainability was 3.60 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

The results imply that the system is secured to be used. Anyone will not have to worry about the system as a whole in general because it was already a feature that takes care of the security especially because the data has something to do with personal data that is protected by the law.

The results are similar with Andal (2023) who emphasized the need for inclusive and comprehensive approaches to address issues such as spatial inequalities, resource gaps, and disparities in learning outcomes, especially in disadvantaged areas.

Table 13

Level of Effectiveness of the Enhanced Enrollment System and Grade Module as Rated by School Administrators and IT Experts: Safety

Indicators	Administrators		IT Experts		Composite	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product or system constrains its operation to within safe parameters or states when encountering operational hazard.	4.00	HE	3.80	HE	3.90	HE

2. The product can identify a course of events or operations that can expose life, property or environment to unacceptable risk.	3.80	HE	3.20	E	3.50	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.90	HE	3.50	HE	3.70	HE

As generated in the table, the administrators assessed the indicators on safety with the overall weighted mean of 3.90 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective while the IT experts rated the indicators with the overall weighted mean of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. The overall weighted mean for the level of effectiveness was 3.70 verbally interpreted as Highly Effective.

This implies that the system is observed to be safe to use by the respondents. Moreover, the information that may impact the system are being dealt with or there is a mechanism to control and save them for the users of the system. Hence, it can be said that the system is safe to be use to its optimal level.

The results are supported by Mina et al (2021) where they said that Open educational resources are freely access, openly licensed hypertext, audio, video, simulations, games and animations that are useful for teaching and learning purposes.

4. Significant Difference on the assessment of the system’s functionality, reliability, and Usability before and After System Development module as assessed by the respondent

Table 14

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the System’s functionality, Reliability, and Usability Before and After System Development

Variables	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Functionality	-0.187	3.06	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
Reliability	-0.340	3.78	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Usability	-0.330	4.19	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: Paired sample t-test at 0.05 significance level, $df = 24$. Negative mean difference indicates higher post-test scores, showing improved system assessment.

As shown in Table, the results of the paired sample t-test reveal that there is a significant difference in the respondents’ assessment of the system’s functionality, reliability, and usability before and after the development of the new enrollment system. All three system components recorded p-values less than 0.05, specifically: functionality ($t = 3.06, p = 0.005$), reliability ($t = 3.78, p < 0.001$), and usability ($t = 4.19, p < 0.001$). These values exceed the critical threshold for significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in all cases.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the enrolment system and grade module improved the enrolment system and grade module. There is no paper to be filled up, waiting time is lessened, and payment method is online. The enhanced enrolment system and grade module is proven to have a pivotal role in the enrollment procedure because it meets the standards set forth in a system for quality

service to be offered to multitude of clientele of the institution. The users may maximize the use of the enhanced enrolment system and grade module with the high assessment on its effectiveness as a system for enrolment and grade viewing; and system's functionality, reliability, and usability before and after the development of the new enrollment system are effective for the enhanced enrolment system and grade module.

Finally, it is suggested that the enhanced enrolment system and grade module be adopted in the furtherance of improved accessibility and convenience which the Institute can offer to its clientele to avoid unnecessary delays; regular system check and updates may be encouraged to continuously improve the system for possible technical flaws thereby assure the users for the system's effectiveness in managing large volumes of data during enrolment period; user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) be continuously monitored to get feedback on the system's software characteristics to ensure interactive user interface; and future IT researchers may investigate other variables that may further improve the enrolment and grade module in educational institutions to maximize the digital technology.

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